

Microwave assisted synthesis and evaluation of some substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles as free radical scavenger

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Manuscript received 21 August 2017, revised 17 February 2018, accepted 31 May 2018

A series of 5-(4-substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4a-h**) were prepared from 4-substituted benzoic acid hydrazides (**3a-h**). Structures of the synthesized compounds were confirmed on the basis of IR, ^{13}C NMR, Mass spectral methods and elemental analysis. The compounds were screened for antioxidant activities using hydrogen peroxide scavenging method comparing with ascorbic acid as standard antioxidant. The results reveal that the compounds possess significant free radical scavenging activities. It is recommended that these compounds might be used in future to generate derivatives for emerging free radical scavenger.

Keywords: Oxadiazoles, microwave synthesis, hydrazides, antioxidant activity.

Introduction

Researchers have proved that microwave irradiation considerably accelerates the several chemical reactions which can be carried out either under solvent-free environment or in less volume of solvent^{1,2}. The microwave irradiated reactions have quickly gained reputation because they are applicable to a range of synthetic conversions using less solvent and rapid heating in the procedures³.

Five membered heterocyclic compounds have their own importance so far as medicinal properties are concerned. Amongst them, 1,3,4-oxadiazoles are considered to be better pharmacophore show a wide range of biological activities^{4,5} like antioxidant⁶⁻⁹, antimicrobial¹⁰⁻¹³, anticonvulsant^{14,15}, immunosuppressive¹⁶, anti-tubercular^{17,18}, anticancer^{19,20} and anti-inflammatory activities^{21,22}. The studies show that the compounds possessing unsubstituted mercapto group (-SH) have prominent free radical scavenging action which can be attributed to replaceable hydrogen and lipophilicity.

Based on these reports, it was thought worthwhile to prepare 1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4a-h**) according to the scheme (Fig. 1) using conventional as well as microwave-assisted (MW) techniques and screen their antioxidant properties.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of 5-(4-substituted)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol.

Results and discussion

The 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives were synthesized as per synthetic scheme (Fig. 1). The structures of compounds **4a-h** were confirmed on the basis of the spectral data (IR, ^{13}C NMR and MS) and elemental analysis which are reported in experimental protocols.

All the compounds showed infra-red peaks at 2640–2560 cm^{-1} (SH group), 1670–1640 cm^{-1} (C=N bond) and 1090–

1070 cm^{-1} (C-O-C bond) justifying the formation of oxadiazole ring. In ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, the compounds showed peak (δ , ppm) at about 171 for C-2 and at 165 ppm approx. for C-5 of 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring. The mass spectrum of title compounds shows that desired molecular ion peaks (M^+) as per molecular weights of the compounds. The elemental analysis reports of the compounds were quite in line with that of the calculated values.

The title compounds were synthesized by using conventional method of heating and also by microwave irradiation in a microwave synthesizer (Catalyst Systems, Scientific Microwave System, Pune, India, CATA R).

A comparison has been made taking into consideration between microwave assisted and conventional methods in respect of yield (%) and reaction time (Tables 1–3). The sequence of reactions to give the desired oxadiazoles **4a-h** is depicted in Fig. 1.

It is well established that antioxidants take part in the omission of free radicals. One of the most important mechanisms to accomplish this objective is the conversion of free

radicals to nonreactive species by donating hydrogen to free radicals²³. Hydrogen donating ability of antioxidants would take out odd electron from highly reactive free radicals²⁴. Many researchers have been studied the effects of different kinds of free radicals in biological systems referring diseases and ageing^{23,24}.

Compounds **4a**, **4b** and **4c** showed moderate whereas **4d**, **4e**, **4f**, **4g** and **4h** displayed high free radical scavenging activity against H_2O_2 (Table 4). Compound **4f** was got the best out of lot with scavenging activity as 92.17 ± 0.81 . The standard, ascorbic acid showed scavenging activity as 72.50 ± 0.92 at same concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

A concentration dependent decrease in H_2O_2 scavenging activity was observed. A study on the molecular weight and the lipophilicity determination points to the fact that the scavenging activities are dependent on the lipophilicity and the size of molecules. A proposed path of a potent compound **4f** has been suggested to justify for the mechanism of free radical scavenging activity based on liable hydrogen of mercapto (-SH) group as shown in Fig. 2.

Table 1. Comparison between conventional and microwave assisted synthesis of methyl 4-substituted benzoate

Compound code	R	m.p./b.p. (°C)	Yield (%)		Reaction time	
			Conventional	MW	Conventional (h)	MW (min)
2a	-F	-/202–204	80.4	82.8	6	6
2b	-Cl	42–44	82.6	85.5	5	5
2c	-Br	80–82	85.6	87.9	6	6
2d	-I	112–14	85.2	87.6	5	8
2e	-CH ₃	33–35	89.2	91.2	4	6
2f	-OH	39–41	88.4	90.1	4	5
2g	-OCH ₃	47–49	87.8	89.5	5	6
2h	-OC ₂ H ₅	51–53	87.2	88.7	6	8

Table 2. Comparison between conventional and microwave assisted synthesis of 4-substituted benzoic acid hydrazide

Compound code	R	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)		Reaction time	
			Conventional	MW	Conventional (h)	MW (min)
3a	-F	158–60	91.3	93.5	6	5
3b	-Cl	161–63	93.4	95.0	5	4
3c	-Br	162–64	94.2	94.8	5	4
3d	-I	174–76	93.8	94.6	5	5
3e	-CH ₃	116–18	94.3	94.8	6	4
3f	-OH	125–27	94.1	94.6	5	3
3g	-OCH ₃	131–33	94.6	95.2	5	4
3h	-OC ₂ H ₅	141–43	94.0	95.4	6	5

Table 3. Comparison between conventional and microwave assisted synthesis of 5-(4-substituted phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol

Compound code	R	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)		Reaction time	
			Conventional	MW	Conventional (h)	MW (min)
4a	-F	174–176	71.2	80.6	7	4
4b	-Cl	180–182	78.5	82.3	7	3
4c	-Br	190–192	86.9	88.4	7	3
4d	-I	212–214	88.6	90.5	7	3
4e	-CH ₃	210–212	82.4	86.7	8	4
4f	-OH	184–186	80.6	84.5	7	3
4g	-OCH ₃	202–204	84.8	88.3	7	4
4h	-OC ₂ H ₅	206–208	87.8	88.2	8	4

Fig. 2. Proposed mechanism for compound **4f** as an antioxidant.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of Merck, Rankem Chemicals and Hi-Media Suppliers from Mumbai, India. Melting points (m.p.) of the compounds were determined using open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of compounds were ascertained by performing Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) on Silica Gel G (chloroform and methanol as mobile phase) and visualized by iodine vapors. IR spectra (in KBr) were taken on a Shimadzu IR Affinity-1 FTIR spectrophotometer and the values are expressed in cm^{-1} . ^{13}C NMR spectra in DMSO were scanned on a Jeol-JMS (400 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as reference standard and the values are

expressed in δ ppm. Mass spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu LC-MS 2010 spectrometer. Elemental analysis was determined using Perkin-Elmer 2400 analyzer. Microwave (MW) assisted reactions were carried out in specially designed reaction vessels of a microwave synthesizer (Catalyst Systems, Scientific Microwave System, Pune, India, CATA-R). The synthesized compounds were recrystallized using aqua ethanol mixtures.

General procedure for microwave assisted synthesis of the compounds:

In our research work, microwave radiation has been used for cutting down the reaction time as compared to conventional heating. So, an attempt was made to correlate the effect of microwave assisted synthesis with that using conventional method^{25,26}.

General procedure for synthesis of substituted benzoate:

The methyl benzoates, **2a-h** were prepared following reported method²⁷ (Table 1).

Microwave method: The same procedure as stated above was adopted using 100 ml methanol following the other conditions of microwave irradiated esterification in reactor at 350 Watt (power) for 5–8 min. All the esters were recrystallized using rectified spirit except **2a**, a fluoro compound which was a liquid (Table 1).

General procedure for synthesis of substituted acid hydrazide:

The benzoic acid hydrazides, **3a-h** were prepared according to reported method in literature^{28,29} with some desirable modifications. The ester (**2a-h**, 0.1 mol) dissolved in appropriate volume of methanol was transferred to a flask with a reflux condenser. Hydrazine hydrate (99%, 0.15 mol)

was slowly added to the mixture and then kept on reflux for about 5–6 h. The excess of solvent and hydrazine hydrate were distilled off. On addition of water the product separated out which was washed several times with distilled water and dried. The product was recrystallized from 80% aqueous ethanol and melting points determined (Table 2).

Microwave method: The same procedure as stated above was adopted using 100 ml methanol following the other conditions of microwave in a microwave reactor at 350 Watt (power) for 3–5 min. Precipitation and separation of precipitate was done as for conventional method (Table 2).

General procedure for synthesis of substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol:

Required acid hydrazide (**3a-h**, 0.1 mol), carbon disulphide (0.12 mol), potassium hydroxide (0.1 mol) and 250 ml methanol were mixed in a flask and refluxed in the fume cupboard^{30,31}. Heating was continued till evolution of hydrogen sulphide stopped (about 8–10 h) which was tested by passing the gas over a filter paper dipped in lead acetate. The excess of solvents were distilled off and then contents diluted with distilled water. The neutralization with dilute hydrochloric acid gave the product. Rectified spirit was used for recrystallization and melting point was determined (Table 3).

Microwave method: The same procedure as stated above was adopted using 140 ml methanol in a microwave reactor at 280 Watt (power) for 3–4 min. Separation of precipitate was done as in conventional method. The product was recrystallized from rectified spirit (Table 3).

5-(4-Fluoro-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (4a):

IR (KBr v, cm^{-1}): 3086 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2542 (S-H str), 1642 (C=N str, ring), 1576–1492 (C=C str, Ar), 1179–1090 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole), 1056 (C-F str); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 169.4 (C-2), 164.7 (C-5), 163.2 (C-4'), 130.2 (C-2',C-6'), 122.2 (C-1'), 115.6 (C-3',C-5'); LCMS: m/z 196 (M^+); Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{FN}_2\text{OS}$): Calcd.: C, 48.97; H, 2.57; N, 14.28; S, 16.34. Found: C, 47.76; H, 2.51; N, 14.17; S, 15.78%.

5-(4-Chloro-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (4b):

IR (KBr v, cm^{-1}): 3094 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2548 (S-H str), 1654 (C=N str, ring), 1586–1482 (C=C str, Ar), 1174–1088 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole), 772 (C-Cl str); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 169.8 (C-2), 164.7 (C-5), 134.8 (C-4'),

129.6 (C-3',C-5'), 128.4 (C-2',C-6'), 124.4 (C-1'); LCMS: m/z 212 (M^+); Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{ClN}_2\text{OS}$): Calcd.: C, 45.18; H, 2.37; N, 13.17; S, 15.08. Found: C, 44.10; H, 2.26; N, 13.07; S, 14.04%.

5-(4-Bromo-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (4c):

IR (KBr v, cm^{-1}): 3096 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2551 (S-H str), 1656 (C=N str, ring), 1584–1494 (C=C str, Ar), 1172–1086 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole), 654 (C-Br str); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 170.4 (C-2), 164.4 (C-5), 132.6 (C-3',C-5'), 129.8 (C-2',C-6'), 125.4 (C-1'), 123.2 (C-4'); LCMS: m/z 257 (M^+); Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{BrN}_2\text{OS}$): Calcd.: C, 37.37; H, 1.96; N, 10.90; S, 12.47. Found: C, 36.9; H, 1.90; N, 10.81; S, 12.02%.

5-(4-Iodo-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (4d):

IR (KBr v, cm^{-1}): 3099 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2554 (S-H str), 1658, (C=N str, ring), 1586–1496 (C=C str, Ar), 1173–1088 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole), 540 (C-I str); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 170.8 (C-2), 164.6 (C-5), 138.4 (C-3',C-5'), 129.6 (C-2',C-6'), 125.2 (C-1'), 94.3 (C-4'); LCMS: m/z 304 (M^+); Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{IN}_2\text{OS}$): Calcd.: C, 31.60; H, 1.66; N, 9.21; S, 10.54. Found: C, 31.02; H, 1.60; N, 9.14; S, 10.47%.

5-(4-Methyl-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (4e):

IR (KBr v, cm^{-1}): 3106 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2558 (S-H str), 2914 (C-H str, aliphatic), 1670 (C=N str, ring), 1566–1462 (C=C str, Ar), 1376 (C-H bend, aliphatic), 1175–1086 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 171.6 (C-2), 164.5 (C-5), 131.8 (C-4'), 127.8 (C-2',C-6'), 125.8 (C-3',C-5'), 123.4 (C-1'), 21.3 (Ar- CH_3); LCMS: m/z 192 (M^+); Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{OS}$): Calcd.: C, 56.23; H, 4.19; N, 14.57; S, 16.68. Found: C, 55.12; H, 3.86; N, 14.48; S, 16.04%.

5-(4-Hydroxy-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (4f):

IR (KBr v, cm^{-1}): 3256 (O-H stretching), 3096 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2539 (S-H str), 1664 (C=N str, ring), 1564–1490 (C=C str, Ar), 1171–1088 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole); ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$): δ 168.6 (C-2), 163.9 (C-5), 157.8 (C-4'), 118.8 (C-1'), 116.6 (C-3',C-5'), 115.8 (C-2',C-6'); LCMS: m/z 194 (M^+); Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$): Calcd.: C, 49.47; H, 3.11; N, 14.42; S, 16.51. Found: C, 48.64; H, 3.01; N, 14.34; S, 16.05%.

5-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (4g):

IR (KBr v, cm^{-1}): 3104 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2908 (C-H

Table 4. Hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives, **4a-h**

Compound code	R	Molecular weight	log <i>P</i>	% Scavenging activity (Mean ± SD)	
				50 (µg/ml)	100 (µg/ml)
4a	-F	196.20	2.54	41.00±0.92	43.67±0.61
4b	-Cl	212.66	2.94	52.40±0.80	56.83±0.75
4c	-Br	257.10	3.21	55.40±0.78	58.97±0.70
4d	-I	304.10	3.74	61.07±0.61	65.13±0.80
4e	-CH ₃	192.23	2.87	63.87±0.76	68.33±0.60
4f	-OH	194.20	1.99	85.10±0.85	92.17±0.81
4g	-OCH ₃	208.23	2.26	70.83±0.91	75.03±0.80
4h	-OC ₂ H ₅	222.26	2.59	68.10±0.80	71.63±0.96
Ascorbic acid	Standard	176.12	-3.36	70.70±0.89	72.50±0.92

str, aliphatic), 2546 (S-H str), 1668 (C=N str, ring), 1558–1464 (C=C str, Ar), 1368 (C-H bend, aliphatic), 1173–1090 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 171.2 (C-2), 164.8 (C-5), 160.5 (C-4'), 118.7 (C-1'), 116.5 (C-2', C-6'), 114.2 (C-3', C-5'), 56.4 (Ar-O-CH₃); LCMS: *m/z* 208 (M⁺); Elemental analysis (C₉H₈N₂O₂S): Calcd.: C, 51.91; H, 3.87; N, 13.45; S, 15.40. Found: C, 50.86; H, 3.16; N, 13.36; S, 14.84%.

5-(4-Ethoxy-phenyl)-[1,3,4]-oxadiazole-2-thiol (**4h**):

IR (KBr ν, cm⁻¹): 3110 (C-H stretching, Ar), 2924 (C-H str, aliphatic), 2552 (S-H str), 1672 (C=N str, ring), 1564–1471 (C=C str, Ar), 1462 (C-H bend, aliphatic), 1178–1092 (C-O-C str, oxadiazole); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ 170.2 (C-2), 165.2 (C-5), 159.8 (C-4'), 118.2 (C-1'), 115.4 (C-2', C-6'), 114.3 (C-3', C-5'), 64.5 (Ar-O-CH₂-CH₃), 15.3 (Ar-O-CH₂-CH₃); LCMS: *m/z* 222 (M⁺); Elemental analysis (C₁₀H₁₀N₂O₂S): Calcd.: C, 54.04; H, 4.53; N, 12.60; S, 14.43. Found: C, 52.96; H, 4.01; N, 12.52; S, 13.92%.

Hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity:

The free radical scavenging activities of the synthesized compounds were evaluated using hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay^{32,33}. This involves the measure of the reduction in the amount of available H₂O₂ using the absorption maxima. In hydrogen peroxide assay, the scavenging activity is determined at 230 nm.

In 10 ml volumetric flasks, 0.6 ml of 40 mM H₂O₂ and 3.4 ml phosphate buffer was added and volume made up. The solution served as control. The synthesized compounds were dissolved in methanol and similarly diluted to represent 50 and 100 µg/ml. These were taken in different 10 ml volumetric flasks taking care that the final concentration of compounds

come out to be 50 and 100 µg/ml as stated above. The volume of H₂O₂ and phosphate buffer as for control, were added and mixed well. After 10 min, the absorbance for each concentration was measured at 230 nm. The % scavenging activity was calculated using following formula,

$$\% \text{ scavenging activity} = [(A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}}] \times 100$$

where, *A*_{control} is the absorbance of the control reaction containing hydrogen peroxide in methanol and phosphate buffer, *A*_{sample} is the absorbance of the test compound. Ascorbic acid, 50 and 100 µg/ml was taken as standard for comparison. The results were represented as mean ± standard deviation (SD) (n = 3).

Conclusions

In the present study, the different 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were synthesized from acid hydrazides and evaluated for antioxidant properties. The syntheses were carried out using conventional and microwave methods and compared with respect to percentage yield and reaction time. The scavenging activities of these compounds were determined using hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay. The results indicated that the synthesized compounds possess moderate to high scavenging activity, as compared to ascorbic acid.

A proposed mechanism of action has been chalked out for future researcher to work in this line to develop new antioxidants.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Analytical Division of Jamia Hamdard, Delhi, India for spectral data. The research facilities provided by Management, GLA University, Mathura (Uttar Pradesh) is gratefully acknowledged.

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